

The Arrival of Peace

...my beloved companion

Peace sought my heart,
Her calm touch, a gentle start.
Her care brought sweet relief,
Like cool rain upon dry earth.

The feeling of love and care,
The warmth of joy,
A solemn expression of happiness
She is a caregiver to weary souls.

With each new sun
Comes a brand-new start,
A new dawn of life
To take the knife from my hand.

Do not take peace for granted.
When she comes, she brings happiness;
She is the doctor of my soul,
And her love makes the heart whole.